

Synthesis, spectroscopic and antibacterial studies on bis(cyclopentadienyl)-hafnium(IV) derivatives with dithiocarbamates derived from α -amino acids

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Abstract : The reactions of bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) dichloride with novel dithiocarbamate ligands [$\text{Na}_2(\text{S}_2\text{C-NH}(\text{R})\text{-COO})$], derived from α -amino acids (glycine, leucine, β -alanine and dl-alanine), have been studied in THF/DMF mixture and binuclear complexes of type $[\{(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{HfCl}\}_2(\text{S}_2\text{C-NH}(\text{R})\text{-COO})]$ have been isolated. Tentative structures of the complexes have been proposed on the basis of analyses, electrical conductance, magnetic moment and spectral (UV-Vis, FT-IR, ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR and FAB-mass) data. NMR spectra indicate that there is rapid rotation of the cyclopentadienyl ring around the metal-ring axis at 25 °C. Studies were conducted to assess the growth inhibiting potential of the ligands and complexes against various bacterial strains. The complexes are found to be potent bactericides than the ligands.

Keywords : Dithiocarbamate, α -amino acid, bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV), synthesis.

Introduction

Dithiocarbamates have been studied extensively over recent decades in response to their growing applications in many areas of analytical chemistry (as pesticides, vulcanization accelerators), industry (flotation agents and high pressure lubricants) and biology (antibacterial, cytostatic, immunoregulatory activities)¹⁻⁷. Most of these applications are based on complexation properties of dithiocarbamate ligands with metal ions. Some papers have appeared on simple dithiocarbamate complexes of Group-4 transition metals^{8,9}. Hafnium(IV) dithiocarbamate derivatives of type $[\text{HfCl}(\eta^2\text{-S}_2\text{CNR}^2\text{R}^3)(\eta\text{-C}_5\text{H}_4\text{R}^1)_2]$ ($\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$ or Me; $\text{R}^2, \text{R}^3 = \text{alkyl}$ or aryl) have been reported¹⁰. In all these derivatives, the dithiocarbamate group coordinates through two sulphur atoms resulting in the formation of four membered chelate rings. It has also been observed that the dithiocarbamate ligands, by virtue of their low charge and small bites ($\sim 2.8\text{-}2.9 \text{ \AA}$), are well suited for stabilization of higher coordination states of metals.

The introduction of the dithiocarbamate group in α -amino acids gives rise to molecules with upto three ligating residues, amino (N), dithiocarbamate ($-\text{CS}_2$) and car-

boxylate ($-\text{COO}^-$). Many proteins have cystein and methionine residues and so dithiocarbamate derivatives of α -amino acids may be valid as models to study the coordination of proteins to metallic cations. However, the complexes formed between metallic cations and dithiocarbamate derivatives of α -amino acids have rarely been reported in the literature^{11,12}.

The present paper describes the synthesis and characterization of bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) derivatives with dithiocarbamates derived from α -amino acids. The structures of the ligands, used for the present work, are shown below (1) :

(1)

Results and discussion

Bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) complexes with dithiocarbamates have been synthesized by the reactions of bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) chloride with sodium salt of dithiocarbamate and complexes of type

$\{[(C_5H_5)_2HfCl]_2(S_2C-NH(R)-COO)\}$ have been obtained. The reactions taking place can be written as :

The elemental analyses (Table 1) indicate 2 : 1 metal to ligand stoichiometry for the complexes. The molecular weights of the complexes, as obtained from the ion peak in FAB-mass spectra, are also given in Table 1. The complexes are light brown to dark brown coloured solids, insoluble in all common organic solvents except in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. The complexes decompose in the temperature range 215–250 °C. The electrical conductance measurements in dimethylformamide reveal that they are essentially non-electrolytes. Magnetic susceptibility values at room temperature

show their diamagnetic nature.

Electronic spectra :

In the electronic spectra of hafnium(IV) complexes, no band appears due to *d-d* transition, which is in accordance¹³ with $(n - 1)d^0ns^0$ configuration of hafnium(IV). A broad band in the region 22600–23500 cm^{-1} appears which can be assigned to charge-transfer band.

Infrared spectra :

The significant infrared spectral bands of bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) complexes are given in Table 2.

Carboxylate group : The most important infrared stretching vibrations belong to that of carboxylato ligands. In the carboxylato complexes, symmetrical O–C–O stretching frequency (ν_1) and asymmetrical O–C–O stretching

Table 1. Preparation, physical properties and analytical data of bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) derivatives with dithiocarbamates of α -amino acids

Reactants taken (molar ratio)	Solvent	Stirring time (h)	Product, Colour, Yield (%)	Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)	Analyses (%) :		
					Found (Calcd.)		
					C	H	Hf
$(C_5H_5)_2HfCl_2 + GDTC.2Na$ (2 : 1)	THF	12	$\{[(C_5H_5)_2HfCl]_2(GDTC)\}$ Light brown, 70	837 (837.4)	32.88 (32.98)	2.70 (2.76)	42.56 (42.63)
$(C_5H_5)_2HfCl_2 + LDTC.2Na$ (2 : 1)	THF	16	$\{[(C_5H_5)_2HfCl]_2(LDTC)\}$ Brown, 65	893 (893.5)	36.0 (36.29)	3.40 (3.49)	39.89 (39.95)
$(C_5H_5)_2HfCl_2 + \beta\text{-ADTC.2Na}$ (2 : 1)	THF	14	$\{[(C_5H_5)_2HfCl]_2(\beta\text{-ADTC})\}$ Brown, 60	851 (851.4)	33.77 (33.85)	2.90 (2.95)	41.86 (41.92)
$(C_5H_5)_2HfCl_2 + dl\text{-ADTC.2Na}$ (2 : 1)	THF	15	$\{[(C_5H_5)_2HfCl]_2(dl\text{-ADTC})\}$ Dark brown, 55	851 (851.4)	33.80 (33.85)	2.88 (2.95)	41.90 (41.92)

where : GDTC.2Na = sodium salt of dithiocarbamate derived from glycine; LDTC.2Na = sodium salt of dithiocarbamate derived from leucine; β -ADTC.2Na = sodium salt of dithiocarbamate derived from β -alanine; dl-ADTC.2Na = sodium salt of dithiocarbamate derived from dl-alanine.

Table 2. Characteristic infrared spectral bands of dithiocarbamates derived from α -amino acids and their corresponding bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) derivatives

Ligand/Complex	Data (cm^{-1})						
	$\nu(N-H)$	$\nu(O-C-O)$	$\nu(S=C=N^-)$	$\nu(CS_2)$	$\nu(Hf-O)$	$\nu(Hf-S)$	$\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$
GDTC.2Na	3200(s)	1680(s), 1260(m)	1500(s)	1260(m), 750(m)	-	-	-
LDTC.2Na	3210(s)	1685(s), 1265(m)	1510(s)	1265(m), 760(m)	-	-	-
β -ADTC.2Na	3200(s)	1670(s), 1270(m)	1500(s)	1270(m), 750(m)	-	-	-
dl-ADTC.2Na	3215(s)	1675(s), 1260(m)	1515(s)	1260(m), 740(m)	-	-	-
$\{[(C_5H_5)_2HfCl]_2(GDTC)\}$	3210(s)	1530(s), 1440(m)	1480(s)	1000(s)	510(m)	360(m)	3000(m), 1420(m), 1025(m)
$\{[(C_5H_5)_2HfCl]_2(LDTC)\}$	3215(s)	1540(s), 1445(m)	1595(s)	980(s)	500(m)	340(m)	3010(m), 1425(m), 1020(m)
$\{[(C_5H_5)_2HfCl]_2(\beta\text{-ADTC})\}$	3200(s)	1535(s), 1440(m)	1480(s)	970(s)	490(m)	350(m)	3015(m), 1415(m), 1025(m)
$\{[(C_5H_5)_2HfCl]_2(dl\text{-ADTC})\}$	3220(s)	1530(s), 1435(m)	1485(s)	1000(s)	495(m)	345(m)	3000(m), 1420(m), 1015(m)

frequency (ν_2) are important, since their position and separation ($\Delta\nu = \nu_2 - \nu_1$) can help in determining the type of bonding with the metal^{14,15}. Coutts and Wailes¹⁶ have studied the infrared spectra of carboxylato derivatives of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(III) and found that the ($\nu_2 - \nu_1$) for benzoato derivative is 80 cm^{-1} and gave the usual bidentate structure. Parashar and Rai¹⁷ have studied the infrared spectra of chromium(III) carboxylato complexes and found that ($\nu_2 - \nu_1$) is of the order of $180\text{--}170 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and gave the bridging structure. Since the infrared spectra of all derivatives exhibit antisymmetric COO^- band at about 1530 cm^{-1} and symmetric COO^- band at about 1430 cm^{-1} , the behaviour of carboxylate groups in the present derivatives may be assigned to bidentate in nature. The difference between two COO^- bands ($\Delta\nu$) has been found to be of the order of $85\text{--}95 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is similar to those found by Coutts and Wailes and confirms the bidentate nature of carboxylate group. The far infrared spectra of all these derivatives show medium bands at *ca.* $510\text{--}490 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned¹⁸ to $\nu(\text{Hf-O})$.

Dithiocarbamate group : The major interest in the preparation of these complexes is to study the effect of the attachment of dithiocarbamate ligand to metal in presence of the carboxylate group, which due to some steric factors might have some effects on the structures of complexes. The different resonating structures of the dithiocarbamate moiety can be represented as below :

The extent to which these resonance forms contribute to the structure and its effect on the physical and chemical properties has been extensively studied. Chatt *et al.*¹⁹, on the basis of a detailed infrared spectral study of a large number of dithiocarbamate complexes, suggested that the resonance form (2, c) does indeed contribute to the structure to a considerable extent, but resonance forms (2, a) and (2, b) too contribute equally to the structure, if dipole moment studies are also taken in to consideration²⁰. Finally, Nakamoto *et al.*²¹ carried out the normal coordi-

nate analysis of the dithiocarbamate metal complexes and concluded that the contribution of the resonance form (2, c) is greater than the others to the total structure of dithiocarbamate complexes and it increases appreciably in *N*-alkyl derivatives.

The strong band, appearing near 1500 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra of ligands, can be assigned to the "thiocarbimido" group $\text{S}=\text{C}=\text{N}^-$. The energy of this band lies intermediate to the stretching frequency associated to C-N bond ($1250\text{--}1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and to C=N bond ($1640\text{--}1690 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), and can best be explained⁷ as a vibration of a polar $\text{C}=\text{N}^+$ bond. Thus, the "thiocarbimido" band near 1500 cm^{-1} implies considerable double bond character in the $\text{S}_2\text{C}\cdots\text{NRR}'$ bond. In general, $\text{C}\cdots\text{N}$ frequency shows a blue shift in the complexes as compared to the respective dithiocarbamate ligand, if the dithiocarbamate group behaves as a bidentate ligand. For a monodentate dithiocarbamate moiety, this frequency should exhibit either no change in position or undergo red shift with respect to the corresponding free ligand frequency. In the complexes, cited here, this frequency undergoes blue shift as compared to free ligands, indicating the bidentate behaviour of dithiocarbamate moiety. The monodentate or bidentate nature of dithiocarbamate group in the ligand is further reflected⁴ in the (C-S) stretching frequency. In case of bidentate behaviour a single strong band appears in the region of $970\text{--}1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, while a doublet is expected in the region of 1000 cm^{-1} for the monodentate one. The complexes, reported in this section, show a single strong band in the region $980\text{--}1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating that both C-S distances are identical and also the bidentate nature of dithiocarbamate group. The $\nu(\text{Hf-S})$ vibration⁸ appears at *ca.* $360\text{--}340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In addition to above bands, the ligands and complexes show one strong band at *ca.* 3200 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu(\text{NH})$. The presence of π -cyclopentadienyl group in these complexes is indicated by the appearance of characteristic bands²¹ at *ca.* 3000 cm^{-1} for $\nu(\text{C-H})$, *ca.* 1425 cm^{-1} for $\nu(\text{C-C})$ and *ca.* 1025 cm^{-1} for $\delta(\text{C-H})$.

Proton magnetic resonance spectra :

The proton magnetic resonance spectra of bis-(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) complexes have been recorded in deuterated dimethylsulphoxide. Chemical shifts

for protons in different environments have been given in Table 3. The complexes show a signal at *ca.* δ 9.60 due to the proton of the NH group. The positions of the signal in the spectra of the complexes are slightly shifted to larger δ values than those of the corresponding ligands and expected from the lower electron density in the complexes than in the ligands. The complexes show signal at δ 6.50–6.75, which may be assigned to the cyclopentadienyl ring protons and indicate the rapid rotation of the ring about the metal-ring axis.

¹³C NMR spectra :

The ¹³C NMR spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO. The complexes show two signals for C₅H₅ rings, indicating unequal environment of the centres to which these rings are attached. For the carboxylic carbon and dithiocarbamate carbon, the signals appear at *ca.* 110.0 and 94.0, respectively. The signals for different carbons are listed in Table 3.

Thus, the above studies suggest that two sulphur atoms and two oxygen atoms of the ligands are involved in chelation. However, coordination of all the donor atoms with single metal atom seems unlikely due to the steric reason. It may be possible that two sulphur atoms from the ligands coordinate to one metal atom while two oxygen atoms of the same ligand coordinate to another metal atom, leading to a binuclear structure (3). The analytical data of the complexes further support binuclear nature. Proposed binuclear structure has also been confirmed by molecular weights as obtained from FAB mass spectra of the complexes.

Antibacterial activity :

The antibacterial activity was evaluated by the paper-disc plate method²². The nutrient agar medium (peptone, NaCl and agar agar) and 5 mm diameter paper discs of Whatman No. 1 were used. The compounds were dissolved in DMSO at 1000 ppm concentrations. The filter paper discs were soaked in different solution of the compounds, dried and then placed in the petriplates previously seeded with the test organism (Gram-positive *Bacillus subtilis* and Gram-negative *Escherichia coli*). The plates were incubated for 24 h at 30 ± 1 °C and the inhibition around each disc was measured in mm.

The results (Table 4) show that activity increases on chelation. The complexes are slightly more toxic than the parent ligands. The complexes show toxicity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. The complex with dithiocarbamate derived from leucine show better activity than derivatives with dithiocarbamate derived from dl-alanine which in turn show better activity than dithiocarbamate derivative with β -alanine or glycine. The activity of the ligands is affected by the nature of substituents, which is related to the lipophilicity of the ligands and their membrane permeability, a key factor in determining their entry inside the cell. The results indicate that branched chain at R gives better activity and as the

Table 3. NMR spectral data (δ scale, ppm) of bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) derivatives with dithiocarbamates derived from α -amino acids

Complex	¹ H					¹³ C			
	$-\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$	NH	CH ₃	CH ₂	CH	$-\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$	-COO-	-CS ₂ -	R
[(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl] ₂ (GDTC)	6.75(s)	9.68(s)	-	4.10(s)	-	115.4, 117.2	110.8	94.7	45.8
[(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl] ₂ (LDTC)	6.50(s)	9.60(s)	1.85(s)	3.85(d)	4.32(d)	115.8, 117.5	110.0	94.1	14.6, 17.5, 21.0, 52.1
[(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl] ₂ (β -ADTC)	6.60(s)	9.65(s)	-	3.70(s)	-	115.6, 117.4	110.4	94.4	40.5, 35.6
[(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl] ₂ (dl-ADTC)	6.62(s)	9.62(s)	1.75(d)	-	4.55(d)	115.5, 117.6	110.5	94.3	18.6, 38.7

Table 4. Antibacterial activity of dithiocarbamates of α -amino acids and their corresponding bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) complexes

Ligand/Compd.	Diameter of inhibition zone (mm)	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>
	(Gram -ve)	(Gram +ve)
GDTC.2Na	7	0
LDTC.2Na	8	7
β -ADTC.2Na	6	7
dl-ADTC.2Na	8	6
[{(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl] ₂ (GDTC)]	9	5
[{(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl] ₂ (LDTC)]	13	12
[{(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl] ₂ (β -ADTC)]	10	8
[{(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ HfCl] ₂ (dl-ADTC)]	12	10
Streptomycin (standard)	20	18

chain length increases the activity also increases.

Experimental

All reactions were carried out strictly under anhydrous conditions. THF was dried by heating under reflux over sodium wire. DMF was dried over anhydrous K₂CO₃. Bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) chloride was purchased from Aldrich. The ligands were prepared by the general method as reported in the literature¹². Microanalyses for C, H and N were performed by the RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow. Sulphur was estimated gravimetrically as barium sulphate. Hafnium was estimated as its oxide²³. Electrical conductance measurements were made on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge type CL01/01 A in nitrobenzene or DMF. The infrared spectra of the ligands and the complexes in the range 4000–200 cm⁻¹ were recorded in potassium bromide medium on Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrometer. The electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer UV-Vis spectrophotometer model 2000. Magnetic susceptibility were made by Faraday balance using ferrous ammonium sulphate as calibrant. The FAB-mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL-SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer using argon/xenon as the FAB gas. The accelerating potential was 10 KV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature.

Preparation of complexes :

To a solution of bis(cyclopentadienyl)hafnium(IV) chlo-

ride (0.02 mol) in THF (50 cm³) appropriate ligand (0.01 mol) dissolved in DMF (10 cm³) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 12–16 h. The solution was filtered and volume of the solution was reduced to ca. 15 cm³ under reduced pressure. Petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80 °C, 15 cm³) was added. The brown coloured precipitate, so obtained, was thoroughly washed with ether and dried *in vacuo*.

The details of the reactions and physical characteristics along with analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

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References

1. D. Coucouvanis, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, **11**, 233; 1979, **26**, 301.
2. J. Willemsse, J. A. Cras, J. J. Steggerda and C. P. Kieijers, *Struct. Bond.*, 1976, **28**, 83.
3. G. D. Thorn and R. A. Ludwig, "The Dithiocarbamates and Related Compounds", Elsevier, New York, 1962.
4. N. Manav, A. K. Mishra and N. K. Kaushik, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2006, **65**, 32 and references therein.
5. R. S. Amim, M. R. L. Oliveira, J. Amim and V. M. D. Bellis, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2006, **31**, 1071.
6. G. J. Perpetuo, M. R. L. Oliveira, J. Janczak, H. P. Vieira, F. F. Amaral and V. M. D. Bellis, *Polyhedron*, 2003, **22**, 3355.
7. A. Bhatt, S. K. Sengupta and O. P. Pandey, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 994.
8. E. Hey-Hawkins, *Chem. Rev.*, 1994, **94**, 1661.
9. F. G. N. Cloke, "Comprehensive Organometallic Chemistry II", Pergamon Press, Oxford, Vol. 4, 1995.
10. S. Kumar, G. S. Sodhi and N. K. Kaushik, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1983, **28**, 357.
11. W. Beck, M. Giernth, M. Castillo and H. Zippel, *Chem. Ber.*, 1978, **111**, 1246.
12. M. Castillo, J. J. Cariado, B. Macias and M. A. Vaquero, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1986, **124**, 127.
13. O. P. Pandey, S. K. Sengupta, B. P. Baranwal, S. K. Shukla and A. Bhatt, *Z. Natureforsch.*, 2001, **56b**, 1.
14. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1997

15. C. Oldham, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **10**, 223.
16. R. S. P. Coutts, R. L. Martin and P. C. Wailes, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1973, **26**, 941.
17. G. K. Parashar and A. K. Rai, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1978, **8**, 427.
18. S. K. Sengupta, O. P. Pandey, A. Bhatt, A. K. Srivastava and K. N. Mishra, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1999, **24**, 703.
19. J. Chatt, L. A. Duncanson and L. M. Venanzi, *Nature*, 1956, **177**, 1042.
20. F. Bonati and R. Ugo, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1967, **10**, 257.
21. K. Nakamoto, J. Fujita, R. A. Condrate and Y. Morimoto, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, **39**, 423.
22. M. Carcelli, P. Mazza, C. Pelizzi, G. Pelizzi and F. Zani, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1995, **57**, 43.
23. O. P. Pandey, S. K. Sengupta, B. P. Baranwal, S. K. Shukla and A. Bhatt, *Z. Natureforsh*, 2001, **56b**, 141.